

A Study on Two Distinguished Culture by poets' on 'Nature'

Dr. Tinni Dutta

Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, Muralidhar Girls' College, Kolkata, India

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*Corresponding author: Dr. Tinni Dutta

Abstract

The concept of culture is the characteristic way of behaving and believing that a group of people in a country or region have evolved over time. Thus a people's culture gives them a sense of who they are, provides them the capacity to adapt to circumstances, affect their emotion and lives. In human history, nature attraction and land cultivation are merged from the perspectives of culture. Natural beauty attracts the poets and they spontaneously reflect it in their writings. It is applicable for both the poets of east & west, especially in Romantic arena. They each require different psychological adaptations and transformations- needs, wishes, conflicts, anxieties and defenses. Wordsworth, Coleridge, Blake, Keats, Datta and Tagore beautifully mingle nature's beauty and sooth human sufferings. We, the human beings, identify with them and feel beauty and joy from our unconscious and are able to transform our owes and pain. They are the symbols of unique cultural identity.

Keywords: Culture, nature, psycho-dynamism, romantic poets.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of culture is the characteristic way of behaving and believing that a group of people in a country or region have evolved over time. Thus a people's culture gives them a sense of who they are, provides them the capacity to adapt to circumstances, affect their emotion and lives. In human history, nature attraction and land cultivation are merged from the perspectives of culture. Natural beauty attracts the poets and they spontaneously reflect it in their writings. It is applicable for both the poets of east & west, especially in Romantic arena. They perceived nature when the power of poetry is strongest and the creative impulse work are untrammelled. It is the union of deep feeling with profound thought, the fine balance of truth in observing with the imaginative faculty.

The art of creating the cultural organization of the environment that would look authentically natural is one of the great invented skills of cultivating the natural environments. Our contemporary efforts to care for the environment by being green are efforts of similar kind. (Valsiner, J, 2014)

The poets' creations are viewable long after the poets' were dead. They could be used as in a linear form of create, use, abandon and re-make.

Blake's the songs of innocence and songs of experience are contrasted elements in a single design. The first one sets out an imaginative vision of the state of innocence and second shows how life challenges and corrupts and destroys it. Childhood is a symbol of a state of a soul which may exist in maturity.

In 'Ancient Mariner' Coleridge visualizes an incredible events through narration which is neo-platonic in nature. According to Bowra(1950) such images of dream are so penetrated with emotional significance. '...such perplexity of mind/as dreams too lively leave behind'.

Wordsworth in his 'Ode to Intimations of Immortality' perceives the beauty of Nature-' There was a time when meadow, grove and stream, /The earth, and every common sight,/ To me did seem/ Apparellled in celestial light, the glory and freshness of a dream/.....The things which I have seen I now can see no more'.

Bowra (1950) has stated Keats was well acquainted with Elgin marbles and it is unlikely that in creating an imaginary work of Greek art he did not consciously or unconsciously owe something to the relics of 'Grecian Grandeur'. The harmony and beauty of the design is splendid and lively today also. Keats says, 'To what green alter, O mysterious priest,/ Lead'st thou that heifer lowing at the skies?'

In east Madhusudan Dutta wondered the beauties of night. And it is a quiet hour when night comes upon the earth calmly, silently and slowly along with the bright gems that reflect upon her sable brow'. It reminds him of those forgotten memories: 'Wakes thoughts of days now past-sunk in the dense/Gloom of oblivion's lethe'. The silence of night has an eloquence. Its stirring breath among the trees' revive past thoughts and brings remembrances of a time when life was sweet of hopes and dreams of childhood which now fleet across the mind in 'solemn silence'. (Dutta, T, 2002).

Tagore in Anasuya (One who feels no envy) live in a lane where the rotting peels of jack-fruit fish scales, ash from the kitchen, corpse of a dead cat is evident. But he feels the smells of paradise flowers. The poet protests against the filthy, harsh reality in which he is compelled to live but which is still unable to throttle romanticism. He goes deep into nature to compensate his frustration imposed by reality. 'My home has no foundation but here is where the flitting maiden flits by. It is spring's when to bind my mind with magic bonds'.

Methodology:

Name of the Poet	Name of the Poem
William Blake	Songs of Innocence & Experience
Samuel Taylor Coleridge	The Ancient Mariner
William Wordsworth	Ode Intimations of Immortality
John Keats'	Ode On A Grecian Urn
Michael Madhusudan Datta	Night
Rabindranath Tagore	Anasuya

Techniques of Analysis:

All selected poems have been analyzed through symbolic and dynamic analysis from cultural perspective to identify the projected thoughts in the theme and title of the poem.

Interpretation

Blake is concerned with the loss of childhood. For him childhood is itself as a symbol of the state of the soul which may exist in maturity. Childhood vision like experience is evident within him. His romantic visions are intermingled with spirituality. He believes God is the creative and spiritual power in man- 'Oh! He gives to us his joy/ That our grief he may destroy: / Till our grief is fled and gone/ He doth sit by us and moan'.

We can utter with Bowra that 'the triumph of 'The Ancient Mariner is that it presents a series of incredible events through a method of narration which makes them not only convincing and exciting but in some sense a criticism of life'. In Ancient Mariner Coleridge visions and dreams are remarkably brilliant and absorbing. Emotions change rapidly but always comes with an unusual force as if the poet was haunted and obsessed by it.

In Ode Wordsworth perceives nature as not merely living its own life but full of beauty and joy. He says 'The Rainbow comes and goes,/ And lovely is the Rose,/ The Moon doth with delight/Look round her when the heavens are bare:/ Waters on a stary night/ And beautiful and fair'. Wordsworth believes that in childhood we see a celestial state that we most value in ourselves.

In Ode on a Grecian urn the opening lines are challenging- 'Thou still unravish'd bride of quietness/Thou foster-child of silence and slow time'. Keats' goes to the heart of the experience which is something beyond sound and beyond change. With the poet we all visualize the urn in all the mystery of its unchanging silence.

In the poem 'Night' by Datta, the symbol of night is related to passive principle, the feminine and the unconscious-expressive of fertility, potentiality and germination'. (Cirlot, J, E, 1962). In the beginning of the poem her power is evident 'in the form of great goddess who created earth and night sky'. At the end a melancholic sadness is reflected. The poet utters 'O Night! Sweet Night! Thy melancholy brow, / Wreathed with those pensive stars, is beautiful'.

The special feature of the poem 'Anasuya' is that here Tagore claims to be a 'born romantic'. In the midst of crises, filth and indecency, civilization is decayed, human values are degraded and life is reduced to ashes, 'streams of blood', 'ocean of tears' but his mind is not shaken. Though he shows stages of repulsion and protests but at the same time he

could feel and perceive the beauties of nature, the song of the bird, and the southerly breeze of the spring and the flow of the river.

CONCLUSION

Despite the cultural barrier, time and space the poetical minds of the east mingles with the minds of west. Their creative imagination is closely connected with emotional insight into an unseen order behind visible things. Therefore their creation is splendid and eternal in nature and has marked significance in these present times.

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